

BIOCOMPOSITE SUBSTRATES FOR WIRELESS SOIL SENSORS

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Keywords: Biobased polymer, Direct Write Process, Natural fiber composite, RFID technology

ABSTRACT

As natural resources continue to become increasingly scarce globally, farming technology for agricultural production to feed the world has been driven to become more precise and efficient. Recently a sensor has been developed to address these needs by directly monitoring the soil environment wirelessly to help improve crop health and yields. The Sensing Earth Environment Directly (SEED) sensor is based on using the direct-write process, radio-frequency identification (RFID) technology, and substrates designed from biobased polymers and natural fibers. For the development of a suitable biocomposite substrate which can support the antenna and circuitry needed for a required time and then degrade into the soil, one must utilize biodegradable polymers such as polylactic acid in combination with natural fibers such as flax fiber as reinforcement to create biocomposites which are compatible with the soil. These biocomposites must be designed to meet critical functional specifications to be used as suitable circuit substrates such as specific flexibility, conductivity, dielectric properties, surface roughness, etc. Flax fiber was selected to reinforce polylactic acid for this application to provide sufficient strength, stiffness, and toughness for the circuitry attached. In this paper, various biocomposites were designed and fabricated to support conductive circuits printed via the direct-write process and tested for integrity through flexural and tensile testing along with dielectric and conductivity measurements. Results from the various flax/polylactic acid biocomposites based on different fiber orientation and fiber loading are presented and discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

The investigation of using a biocomposite substrate as the foundation for electronic devices has become a need in the circuit board industry to enable more sustainable ways of sourcing materials and manufacturing. Many applications with a need for a biobased printed circuit board (BPCB) exist mainly in the area of precision agriculture. In this work, biocomposite substrates were printed with conductive bioinert metals to facilitate radio-frequency identification (RFID) technologies creating a passive, direct writing form of sensors. These sensors are referred to as Sensing Earth Environment Directly (SEED) sensors and are envisioned to monitor the moisture and nutrient content of the soil throughout agricultural fields wirelessly.

2 GENERAL SPECIFICATIONS OF BPCB

For a BPCB to be properly utilized in production, it must be able to conform to certain current PCB physical standards. If this is a process that is unable to be replicated on a large scale, BPCBs will only be able to be utilized in very niche markets. For the envisioned SEED sensor, the BPCBs must not only be able to biodegrade within a certain time frame, but also support the circuitry for the required time as well. Therefore, not only is biodegradation an important requirement, but the typical PCB requirements of flexibility, strength, conductivity, etc. are also critical. To achieve these requirements in this work, a biodegradable polymer reinforced with a natural fiber was demonstrated. The structure chosen for this application was a polylactic acid (PLA) polymer matrix reinforced with a woven mat of flax fiber.

2.1 Materials for Manufacturing

To manufacture the BPCBs in this study, different materials were sourced from various manufacturers. As the matrix of the composite structure must be both biodegradable and nonconductive, PLA was selected for this application. PLA has similar material properties to ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE). UHMWPE has been used in PCB manufacturing as a singular substrate in the past [1]. With PLA selected, two different film thicknesses were purchased to help optimize the manufacturing method. The PLA selected was from McMaster-Carr at thicknesses of 0.178 mm and 0.381 mm (0.007" and 0.015") [2]. Another form of PLA was also used to increase the wetting of the fibers in the mold, a PLA powder. This powder was acquired from ICO Polymers. The second component of the BPCB was the fiber reinforcement. Again, because biodegradability and nonconductivity are the main objectives of the BPCB substrate, flax fiber was selected to act as the reinforcement. The flax fiber selected was comingled with PLA fiber into a fabric. The flax/PLA fabric was purchased from Composites Evolution, Biotex Flax 2x2 Twill 400gsm [3]. Both the flax fiber used and the PLA are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flax fiber and PLA material forms used.

The last component for a BPCB layup was a thin layer of conductive material. Two different types of copper layers were selected for experimentation. A copper shim stock was used from Lyon Industries in a roll of 127 cm (50") long, 15.24 cm (6") wide and 0.0254 mm (0.001") thick [4]. The second form of copper used was a screen-like layer, 100x100 mesh, and 0.114 mm (0.0045") wire diameter, from McMaster-Carr. A third electrically conductive material, Aluminium, was also used to test the differences in resistivity to ultimately provide a functioning board at a lower cost with less environmental impact. It was the same dimensions as the copper shim stock.

A secondary process, Micro Cold Spray (MCS), was explored to build up a conductive paths on the surface of a PLA rich surfaced BPCB as an additive manufacturing approach. In this process silver traces, copper traces, and aluminium traces have all been tested to-date with varied success.

3 EXPERIMENTATION

3.1 General Processing Requirements

In order to create biocomposites which could meet the physical properties needed for PCB replacement, three basic parameters were managed. The first was to ensure the PLA resin had properly wet the fibers to limit delamination potential. The second was to monitor the processing parameters

such that the material underwent negligible thermal degradation in both the flax fiber and the PLA. The third was to monitor the thickness of the finished BPCB to be 5 ± 1 mm thick in order to conform to typical PCB characteristics.

3.2 Different Layups Tested

The required thickness was achieved after several processing trials. The final layup ensured proper wetting through the addition of layers of thin PLA where there was only a single layer of thin PLA used in previous panels. The final layup also contained strategic placement of powdered PLA to improve wetting of the flax fiber. However, future work is required in manufacturing to ensure a repeatable process to produce consistent quality BPCB.

Subsequent panels were fabricated like those explained above, except these layups included copper or aluminium in the outermost surfaces. The copper was placed on top of the Thick PLA in both instances. One layup used copper shim stock, whereas the other layup used copper mesh. Each layup containing copper appeared to properly wet, exhibit minimal degradation, and achieved the thickness required. Material layup for three of the composites can be seen in Figure 2 below. The aluminium composite can be seen in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Finished layups with outer copper film (left), no copper film (center), and outer copper mesh (right).

Figure 3. Finished Aluminum Layup.

3.3 Different Molding Methods

During the processing of the BPCBs it was found that simple compression molding was most suitable for applying controlled heat, pressure, and duration. A Carver Press seen in Figure 4 was used to compression mold all of the substrates. Each parameter of the compression molding process was limited by both the PLA and flax fiber properties as the copper and aluminium material properties for heat and pressure were much higher than the PLA and flax fiber. The upper temperature limit used and pressures achieved during processing were provided for the Biotex Flax Fiber. The specified values from the supplier were molding temperatures of 175-200°C and pressures between 1-10 MPa.

Figure 4. Carver Press used to compression mold biocomposite panels.

The compression mold comprised of an upper mold that was a rectangular block of steel that was 100 mm X 200 mm length and width, with a thickness of 48 mm. This block of steel was placed in the lower mold. This mold was used in every layup process to manufacture the BPCBs. To protect the PLA from sticking to the mold, a layer of non-porous Teflon coated fiberglass was used on both the upper and lower mold.

Many different compression molding parameters were varied until the optimal process was realized. The final compression molding method utilized 3.5 MPa of pressure at 190 °C for 1 hour followed by 6 hours of ambient cooling time. In addition, the mold was preheated to the desired temperature of 190 °C prior to the introduction of the biocomposite preform layup. The mold was then taken out of the press, the composite layers were quickly added, and then the mold was placed back in the oven for a 1 hour. This method was used for making all of the BPCBs tested.

4 RESULTS

The biocomposite substrates manufactured were trimmed from larger panels into both tensile coupons and coupons for conductive printing and prototype sensor development. The following sections describe the tensile, conduction, and sensor development results to-date.

4.1 Different Molding Methods

After processing all three biocomposite layups, some basic material properties were characterized. A 30kN Instron load frame was used to measure the tensile properties of the different biobased substrates produced using ASTM standards [5]. The strength and modulus values of the various biocomposite layups and fiber orientations are shown in Figure 5 below. This evaluation of tensile properties allowed a better comparison of the effects of adding the different copper layers to the layup.

As seen by the tensile results, it is clear that the shim stock copper along the longitudinal direction of the fabric achieved the highest overall strength and modulus. This type of layup is favored if wanting to simulate a typical fiberglass PCB. This structure would allow for easier manufacturing in a printing house, as there would be less of a need to calibrate equipment to run these BPCBs. A typical fiberglass PCB consists of glass fiber reinforced epoxy resin that has a sheet of copper bonded to one or both sides. Glass fiber in roll form is coated with liquid resin. The wet roll is fed through rollers to obtain the needed thickness, cut into sheets and semi cured. Copper cladding is then sandwiched on each side of the sheet and the stack-up is bonded together in a high pressure heated press. Fully cured sheets then go through a process of drilling via holes and selective copper removal by either selective chemical photo lithographic processes or mechanical milling to create circuitry patterns on one or each side of the sheet, thus creating a circuit board [6]. Adding copper or aluminium sheeting to the PLA/flax fiber layup during compression molding was a very easy facilitated process which then transformed the PLA/flax biocomposite sheet into a machinable biobased circuit board material.

Figure 5. Strength and modulus measured for each of the layups and orientations of the biocomposites processed.

SEED sensor circuit boards for proof-of-concept were first manufactured from typical FR4 circuit board material that was 1.465 mm (0.0577") thick core with 28 g (1 oz), 0.0318 mm (0.00125") copper cladding on each side giving a total thickness of 1.524 mm (0.060") for process development and comparison to the biocomposite prototype material which had a core thickness of 1.778 mm (0.070") with 0.0508 mm (0.002") copper cladding on each side giving a total of 1.879 mm (0.074"). The FR4 circuit board material was specifically Isola ED130UV with 28 g (1 oz) copper cladding which utilizes a di-functional epoxy resin core with modified tetra epoxy face plies for ultraviolet protection. Tensile strength of the FR4 material was 345 MPa longitudinal and 276 MPa transverse [7]. Tensile modulus of the board material was 24 GPa longitudinal and 21 GPa transverse [7].

4.1 Conductive Path Printing Success

The strength of the BPCB board is important, but once a board with sufficient properties is obtained, the actual circuitry on the board becomes the next important factor. For a proof of concept, direct-written traces were printed on the BPCB board using the in-house technique of Micro Cold Spray [8]. This tool allows for the deposition of metallic features on temperature sensitive substrates without post-processing steps such as sintering. For initial tests both copper and silver features were printed to pattern consisting of a 1 cm long line with 1 mm pads on each end. The resistance of the features was measured using a Fluke 177 multimeter as shown in Figure 6. Here the resistance between example traces about 100 μm wide was 125 Ω . This confirms basic feasibility of this additive manufacturing approach on the BPCBs. When the features were printed with silver, resistances as low as 2.0 Ω were achieved.

Figure 6. Multimeter test of 1 cm long printed copper traces on BPCB.

Using MCS technologies, with a new nozzle, different passes of aluminium traces were also tested. There were multiple paths made during the process to find the optimal path width and resistance. The

paths tested varied from 3 paths to 15 paths. The best results occurred with 15 passes and resulted in a minimal resistance of 0.8 Ω . The results from these different tests can be seen in Table 1.

Sample #	Print Passes	Resistance (Ω)	Line Width (μm)
1	3	7.5	262
2	5	2.6	393
3	7	1.5	444
4	9	1.1	549
5	15	0.8	790

Table 1. Summary of Print pass results with Aluminium Traces.

With MCS process, some porosity is created in the traces which could lead to mechanical weakening of the traces over time. An SEM image of aluminium on the bicomposites using MCS can be seen in Figure 7. Another concern with adhesion can be seen where delamination appears between the aluminium and PLA interfacial surface. These aspects of printing on the biocomposites using MCS will be optimized in future work.

Figure 7. SEM image of 15 passes illustrating deposition porosity

4.1 SEED Sensor Developments

For the prototype SEED sensor, the PLA/flax fiber PCB with copper shim was utilized. The copper traces were mechanically milled using a standard prototyping process at NDSU in the Center for Nanoscale Science and Engineering (CNSE). An LPKF S100 circuit board milling machine was used to mill away the copper cladding material in a specific circuit and antenna pattern and to drill through holes which are later filled with conductive ink to create conductive vias to connect the top and bottom side ground planes of the circuit board [9]. A clear enamel coating was manually applied to create solder stop mask on circuitry traces where no solder was desired to flow. Low temperature solder was used to manually solder on the standard commercially off the shelf surface mount components consisting of an RFID land grid array package, one resistor, and two capacitors as the resin beneath the copper cladding of the circuit board had a low melting point. Once the components were installed, the RFID circuit of the sensor was tested by placing the sensor near an RFID reader. The RFID circuit was successfully read by the reader illustrating that the circuitry made on the prototype bicomposite board functioned properly. This sensor was then compared with FR4 board based prototypes and all had comparable RFID read distances in open air of approximately 1-1.5 m (3-5 ft) from the RFID reader.

The finished SEED moisture sensor is displayed in Figure 8. Some challenges with assembly of the BPCBs including delamination of the copper from the biocomposite did exist and future work is needed to optimize. The aluminium prototype seen in Figure 9 has yet to show signs of delamination. The process of strategically adding PLA powder in the aluminium boards greatly increased wetting and provided a better structure.

Figure 8. PLA/Flax SEED sensor prototype.

Figure 9. PLA/Flax/Aluminium SEED sensor prototype.

5 CONCLUSIONS

With the completion of this study, it was found that using a PLA/flax fiber biocomposite as a substrate is a viable option for biobased circuit boards. The mechanical properties, however lower than traditional PCB material, were found to be acceptable to print conductive traces for establishing circuitry for the SEED sensor. In addition, the resistance measured across conductive traces printed onto the BPCBs were acceptable for circuit features envisioned to be attached to the SEED sensor. Finally, the biocomposite substrate seen in Figure 9 is conductively operable and ultimately proves that this BPCB has utility upon future modifications and optimization.

5.1 Future Work

While the results of this project were promising, there have been several areas of improvement identified to further optimize the BPCBs. There was delamination starting between the MCS trace and the PLA found in some of the BPCBs processed. This will lead to quicker biodegradation than what is required and possibly the lack of conductivity. To ensure the highest quality of these BPCBs, different MCS settings will be tested and more PLA will be added to the surface to increase bonding. After this is completed it is planned to trace an entire circuit using MCS rather than the traditional techniques used now with the BPCBs.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Funding for this research project was provided by the North Dakota Department of Commerce – Venture Grant Program, 14-11-J1-75.

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